

A NOTE ON THE OCCURRENCE OF AN ISOMER OF RICINOLEIC ACID IN THE FATTY OIL FROM THE SEEDS OF *VERNONIA ANTHELMINTICA*.

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The fatty oil from the seeds of *Vernonia Anthelmintica* (N. O. *Compositae*) has been examined for its physical and chemical constants by Menon (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1910, 29, 1431). He does not mention that the oil has got any acetyl value or any optical rotation. We have observed that the oil possesses an optical rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{25}, -10.7$ and an acetyl value of 135.1. The optical rotation and acetyl value are not entirely due to the high percentage of non-saponifiables, generally found in the oil extracted by a solvent. The mixed fatty acids of the oil, free from the non-saponifiables, have been found to have an acetyl value of 118.2 and optical rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{25}, -7.2$. They contain about 60% of the total weight a hydroxy straight chain acid belonging to monohydroxy octodecenoic (ricinoleic acid) series. This acid is sparingly soluble in petroleum ether, which makes its separation from other saturated fatty acids fairly easy. It is viscous just like ricinoleic acid and has a saponification equivalent of 299.0 (calc. for $C_{18}H_{34}O_3$: 298.2).

Bussy and Lecanu (*J. Pharm.*, 13, 57) found that castor oil from the seeds of *Ricinus Communis* contains a high percentage of ricinoleic acid which is *d*-rotatory and has an optical rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{25}, +6.2$ to $+7.5$ (Walden, *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 3472). The constitutional formula assigned to this acid by Goldsobel (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 3121) and later on verified by Haller and Brochet (*Compt. rend.*, 1910, 496) is

The hydroxy-acid, obtained from the oil of *Vernonia Anthelmintica* seeds differs from ricinoleic acid. It is *l*-rotatory having an optical rotation of $[\alpha]_D^{25}, -7.8$. The hydroxy group appears to be in different position. It has been observed that the hydroxy group is very easily substituted by halogens, even during the period of iodine value determination by Wij's or Hanus solution. When the acid is acetylated and the hydroxy group is protected no more substitution takes place and the exact quantity of iodine only at the ethylenic linkage is absorbed. (I. V. of the acid, 108.4. Found I. V. for acetylated acid 73.8. Calc. for $C_{20}H_{36}O_4$: I. V., 74.4). It differs from the quince oil acid also in that it does not give

a solid dibromide whereas the quince oil acid has been reported to give a dibromide, m.p. 108° (Herrmann, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1899, 237, 366).

Further work on the constitution of this acid and chemical examination of the other constituents of the oil is in progress.

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